

Modeling Middle-Ear Acoustic Input Impedance of Cochlear-Implanted Ears

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Abstract. Cochlear implantation may disrupt the mechanical integrity of the middle ear, potentially affecting residual low-frequency hearing and measurements of electrically evoked stapedial reflexes, which are useful for mapping the electrode array. Wideband acoustic immittance (WAI) is a promising tool for estimating middle-ear input impedance. However, the presence of acoustic sources that do not contribute to stapes displacement can confound these estimates. This study utilized data from (Scheperle, R. A., & Hajicek, J. J. (2020). *Ear and hearing*, 41(4), 883), which included WAI measurements from normal hearing (NH) and cochlear implanted (CI) ears. We evaluated changes in middle-ear stiffness between NH and CI ears using a preliminary model of the middle ear organized to represent its structural anatomy. This model aims to improve impedance estimates by removing confounding influences such as from ear canal acoustics. Absorbance and middle-ear input admittance were compared between CI and NH groups. Notably, the CI group had significantly reduced low-frequency middle-ear admittance magnitude between 0.25-0.92 kHz and increased admittance between 3.34-3.59 kHz. Admittance phase was Significant differences in admittance phase were observed between 0.36 - 1.23 and 3.16 - 3.52 kHz. The middle-ear impedance estimation method shows promise for (1) differentiating ears with normal and abnormal tympanometry and (2) quantifying impedance changes after implantation or, possibly, during the implantation surgical procedure. The low-frequency decrease observed in admittance magnitude for the CI group indicates an increased stiffness in the tympanic membrane, especially for the CI ears with abnormal tympanometry.

INTRODUCTION

Wideband Acoustic Immittance (WAI) measurements can potentially evaluate middle-ear status over most of the hearing frequency range. Cochlear implantation may alter the mechanical integrity of the middle ear. An intact middle ear after surgery is essential for preserving low-frequency acoustic hearing and clinical measurement of electrically evoked stapedial reflexes/thresholds (eSRT), which are useful for programming the CI processor. The cochlear implant electrode array is typically inserted into the round or oval window via the middle ear. Insertion of the electrode array may also cause intracochlear changes that affect stapedial motion.

WAI measurements are typically expressed as reflectance or absorbance. Reflectance and absorbance measurements from cochlear implant recipients suggest these ears have increased middle-ear stiffness after implantation, especially at low frequencies (Scheperle & Hajicek, 2020; Merchant et al., 2020). WAI can be used to estimate middle-ear input impedance but standing waves and acoustic reflections that do not translate to stapes displacement may confound estimates. More precise estimates of middle-ear impedance, as it relates to audition, can be obtained by accounting for ear-canal acoustics (Rasetshwane & Neely, 2011; Lewis & Neely, 2015) and middle-ear cavity resonance. These can be mitigated by decomposing WAI measurements with a lumped-element model of the middle ear (Lewis & Neely, 2015; Merchant & Neely, 2023). Arranging model components to correspond to physiology further improves the predictive insight into middle ear status. For example, Merchant & Neely (2023) used a middle-ear model to improve clinical diagnostic detection of otitis media with effusion in children with wideband absorbance.

In the present study, we utilize previously published wideband reflectance data (Scheperle & Hajicek, 2020) measured in a normative group with normal hearing (NH) and a second group that received a cochlear implant (CI). Based on statistical differences between reflectance measurements, it was suggested that the CI group should have increased middle-ear stiffness at frequencies <1 kHz and a small region around 4 kHz (Scheperle & Hajicek, 2020). However, the methods used in that study did not allow quantification of middle ear impedance. In this study, we expanded the lumped-element analog circuit model of Lewis and Neely (2015) to be more physiologically representative of middle-ear anatomy. WAI acoustic measurements from Scheperle and Hajicek (2020) were recomputed to extend the usable frequency range and then decomposed with a modified lumped element model (see Fig. 1) from where middle-ear impedance, expressed as admittance was estimated.

METHODS

Ear-Canal and Middle-Ear Model

Figure 1 shows the analog circuit model of ear canal acoustics and the middle ear, which was used to decompose WAI measurements. This lumped element model is a modified version of the middle-ear model described by Lewis and Neely (2015). Additional branches have been added to the model and they are organized closer to the physiology of the middle ear.

The ear-canal input impedance Z_{ec} is defined at the plane of the probe microphone. The ear canal is modeled as a non-uniform transmission line representing six concatenated truncated-cone segments (Rasetshwane & Neely, 2011; Rasetshwane et al., 2012). Middle-ear input impedance Z_{me} is defined at the tympanic membrane. Acoustic energy that does not contribute to the motion of the ossicular chain is represented by the branches of the middle-ear network (K_2, R_2, M_2) and (K_4, R_4, M_4). It is unclear what structures contribute to the anti-resonances these branches. Hence, we are labeling them “to-be-determined” (TBD), but we can confirm these network components are important for fitting the model to the data. The remaining components of the middle ear may be associated with anatomical structures by comparison with previous middle-ear network models (e.g., Kringlebotn, 1988): stapes (K_1, R_{st}, M_1), malleus and incus (K_3, R_3, M_3), incudostapedial joint (K_5, R_5), and cochlear load (R_{co}), which is in series with the stapes so, $R_1=R_{st}+R_{co}$.

Wideband Acoustic Immittance Measurements

WAI measurements from Scheperle and Hajicek (2020) were used for this study, which consisted of 28 normal hearing (NH) ears and 14 ears with a cochlear implant (CI), three of which had abnormal tympanometry. The NH group served as a normative group for comparison.

WAI measurements were made using an ER10C otoacoustic emission probe (Etymotic Research, Elk Grove, IL) connected to an RME Babyface. A custom software module written in MATLAB was used to run with the ARLas (<https://github.com/myKungFu/ARLas>) software suite and was modified to acquire measurements and perform the calibration. Thevenin source probe calibrations were performed before each participant. Wideband reflectance measurements were made using a chirp with a flat frequency response from 0.2 to 20 kHz. For this study, the raw data was used to extract the entire frequency range of the WAI measurements to be compatible with the range expected by the middle-ear model.

Wideband Acoustic Immittance Measurement Decomposition

Impedance was estimated with the LEM middle-ear network, and its components were arranged according to structural anatomy (see Fig. 1). The impedance estimation method removes confounding influences from WAI measurements such as ear canal standing waves, resonances, and unknown sources that cause a notch in absorbance (or a peak in reflectance), typically observed between 7 and 10 kHz (e.g., Lewis and Neely, 2015). This antiresonance may arise from either a non-propagating mode of tympanic membrane vibration, or higher order modes of the middle-ear cavity, or both. This anti-resonance is a common feature of WAI measurements and appears independent of sound intensity when observed in psychophysical data (e.g., Rasetshwane et al., 2015). Model parameters of the middle-ear network were fit to individual WAI data by finding the global minimum with a constrained multivariable search using 9000 iterations a (i.e., see the MATLAB function `fminsearch`).

Figure 1. An analog circuit model of ear-canal acoustics and middle-ear mechanics was modified from the model described by Lewis and Neely (2015). The ear-canal input impedance Z_{ec} is defined at the plane of the probe microphone. The middle-ear input impedance Z_{me} is defined at the tympanic membrane. The initial branch of the middle-ear network (K_2, R_2, M_2) is labeled “to-be-determined” (TBD) but could be the result tympanic membrane vibration that does not contribute to the motion of the ossicular chain is represented by the. The remaining components of the middle ear may be associated to anatomical structures by comparison with previous middle-ear network models (e.g., Kringelbotn 1988): stapes (K_1, R_{st}, M_1), malleus & incus (K_3, R_3, M_3), incudostapedial joint (K_5, R_5), possible middle-ear cavity resonance/TBD (K_4, R_4, M_4), and cochlear load (R_{co}), which is in series with the stapes, so $R_1=R_{st}+R_{co}$.

RESULTS

Absorbance levels for each group are plotted in Fig. 2, with (a) showing the normal-hearing group, (b) the CI-implanted ears that had normal tympanometry, and (c) CI-implanted ears that had abnormal tympanometry. The dashed black line is the mean for each subgroup.

Figure 2. Absorbance levels expressed in dB for the normative group in (a), the CI-implanted ears with normal tympanometry in (b), and the CI-implanted ears that had abnormal tympanometry (c). The dashed black line is the mean within each subgroup.

Figure 3. Decomposed WAI measurements expressed as admittance, $Y = \frac{1}{Z}$, magnitude (top left panels) and phase (bottom left panels) and absorbance on the right-hand panels for a normal hearing (Female, age 23) participant (left hand panels) and a participant with a cochlear implant and normal tympanometry (right hand panels). Ear canal absorbance is what is typically measured in the clinic and is relatively unaffected by ear canal acoustics. However, canal admittance, Y_{EC} , is shown as the blue line in the left-hand panels and is confounded by ear canal acoustics such as standing waves. The red lines show is the estimate middle ear admittance, Y_{ME} , which is the input admittance to the middle ear after the influence of the ear canal has been removed. The 226 Hz tympanometry data for the same participants are shown in Table 1 for comparison, where ECV is the equivalent ear canal volume (ECV) in mmho, tympanic peak pressure (TPP) in decapascal, tympanometric width, and admittance (Y_a).

TABLE 1. 226 Hz tympanometric measurements for the normal and CI-implanted ears shown in figure 3. ECV (ear canal volume), Y_a (admittance), TPP (tympanometric peak pressure).

	ECV mmho	TPP daPa	Tymp Width	Y_a mmho
Normal Hearing	1.07	5	99	0.53
Cochlear Implanted	1.62	-71	86	0.88

Figure 3. Ear-canal (Y_{EC}) and middle-ear admittance (Y_{ME}) and absorbance for a NH participant (female, 23 years old) (left panels) and a CI implanted ear with normal tympanometry (right panels). The top left panels for each group are admittance magnitude ($|Y|$) phase (bottom left). The estimated middle-ear admittance (Y_{ME}) is the admittance after removing the influence from standing waves within the ear canal. The top right panels show absorbance which is typically measured with WAI clinical devices.

In the left column of Fig. 4, the measured admittance magnitude and phase are shown for each group. In the right column, the corresponding modeled middle-ear fit is shown which is like a smoothed version of the measurements. Note the reduced admittance < 1kHz for both groups of CI-implanted ears, where the red line corresponds to CI ears that had normal 226 tympanometry and the yellow line for CI ears with abnormal tympanometry.

Figure 4. Means for the Measured vs. Modeled Middle ear output for each group. "Normal" is the normative group, CI-Imp-Norm is the CI-implanted ears with normal tympanometry, CI-Imp-Ab is for the CI-implanted ears with abnormal tympanometry.

Fig. 5. Shows the group means for each group where blue is for NH and red for CI ears of standard ear canal (EC) absorbance (left) and middle ear admittance after removal of the ear canal. Schepeler and Hajicek (2020) observed

decreased absorbance <1 kHz and near 4 kHz in the CI group, which they interpreted as an increased stiffness. Our results confirm stiffness increased <1 kHz but not at 4 kHz, as expected. We also observed decreased stiffness in $|Y_{ME}|$ between 1 and 2 kHz, which was not anticipated from the absorbance measurement.

Figure 5. Ear-canal absorbance (left) and middle-ear admittance group means (normal hearing, blue, all CI ears, red). All ears within both groups had normal 226 tympanometry. Note that CI ears include those with abnormal tympanometry.

A Wilcoxon rank-sum test (Mann-Whitney U) was used to compare the distributions of the two groups with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Analysis was performed on ear canal absorbance, magnitude ($|Y_{ME}|$) and Y_{ME} phase over the frequency range of 0.2 to 10 kHz. The test identified differences in ear canal absorbance for frequencies over the ranges 0.245-0.915 and 3.34-3.59 kHz. Significant differences were observed in admittance magnitude between 0.2-0.38 and 1.59-1.595 kHz and admittance phase between 0.36-1.225 and 3.16-3.523 kHz. These findings suggest that middle ear admittance is influenced by cochlear implantation at specific frequency points.

DISCUSSION

In this paper, we presented a lumped element model designed to decompose WAI measurements into acoustic components that also mitigate the influence of ear-canal acoustics enabling estimates of middle-ear admittance or impedance. To demonstrate the feasibility of this model, we used the previously published data from Schepeler and Hajicek (2020) to further quantify the differences in middle ear impedance between a group of normative ears and those with CI. We showed a decreased absorbance < 0.915 kHz and increased absorbance around 3.5 kHz which consistent with the findings of Schepeler and Hajicek (2020). However, when investigating middle ear admittance, the frequency regions where significant differences emerged were more closely related to admittance phase rather than magnitude. The phase of both groups is positive < 2 kHz indicating stiffness dominance which trends towards mass dominance >2 kHz.

It is important to remove the influence of ear-canal acoustics when analyzing admittance, as it is susceptible to the effects of standing waves and resonance. Each component of the proposed model plays a crucial role for fitting WAI data. However, currently, we are cautious about drawing direct correlations between the model's branch-level parameters and anatomical structures. While the model is preliminary, further refinement of its parameter space offers potential for interpreting both admittance and absorbance in relation to individual middle ear structures. Although fit errors were within acceptable limits, within-group variations in parameter means (not shown) and their standard deviations suggest the need for additional constraints on model parameters.

In Figure 1, we noted that the second and fourth network branches are essential for achieving an optimal fit for WAI data. Nevertheless, the anatomical structures corresponding to these anti-resonances remain uncertain. The 2nd branch (K_2, R_2, M_2) may correspond to an unpropagated mode of the tympanic membrane that propagates to the middle ear cavity. The presence of a notch in admittance between 8–10 kHz is a common characteristic of WAI measurements, even after accounting for ear canal acoustics and corresponds to (K_4, R_4, M_4) and may be due to a higher mode of vibration that cannot be explained by plane wave propagation. We are confident in the ear canal compensation methodology used in this study (Rasetshwane & Neely, 2011; Rasetshwane et al., 2012), and available evidence indicates that these notches in admittance may be attributed to middle ear structures.

CONCLUSIONS

We suggest that Y_{ME} is a more relevant indicator of the underlying conductive mechanism than absorbance because Y_{ME} is a mechanical measure closely tied to the middle ear, especially after eliminating the influence of the ear canal. Relative to absorbance, middle ear admittance does not vary with cross sectional area which may reduce variability across individuals due to ear-canal acoustics. Furthermore, admittance has the potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy over absorbance due to the availability of both magnitude and phase.

After isolating the propagating components of the middle ear, we could confirm cochlear implanted ears have increased stiffness <0.38 kHz the real part of admittance and phase indicates these ears are less stiffness dominated and more damped than normal ears <1.2 kHz. The additional analysis with this model after measurement takes seconds and requires no additional cost or equipment. While this model is preliminary, improvements are expected by adding more physiologically relevant constraints to the fitted parameter values.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Panagiota Kitsopoulos]: Great paper! I am very interested in the middle ear lumped element model. Below are a few comments/questions. In the Methods, you mention that the TBD section is an important component (even though it is unclear what structure contributes to it). Was this confirmed experimentally and then compared with your model with and without the TBD section?

[Joshua Hajicek]: Thanks Penny, this is a great question. There are two branches we labelled "to be determined" (TBD) that correspond to two notches in absorbance. Branch 2 is associated with a notch between 1-2 kHz and the 4th branch between 8-10 kHz. Model fits are much better when these branches are included and at this time is largely an empirical observation but over many ears, not just the for the ears presented here. We remain conservative about labelling the 2nd and 4th branches but discuss possibilities in the text.

[Panagiota Kitsopoulos]: Do you find that combining the malleus and the incus is a good estimation, or should we be looking at them separately?

[Joshua Hajicek]: We based our model arrangement off Kringelbotn (1988) who also represented these ossicles as a single resonance. The benefit of modeling these ossicles separately is currently unclear.

[Panagiota Kitsopoulos]: Could you talk a little more about how you fit the model parameters and the reasoning behind the method you used to fit them?

[Joshua Hajicek]: We used a multivariable search based on Lagarias et al. (1998) which converges quickly for the number of parameters we are using. A potential issue with this method is there are typically more than one local minimum so there is a chance you miss the parameter set that achieves the true global minimum. Another possibility would be to use gradient based search methods for optimizing the parameter fits, which is typically better for larger parameter spaces.

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[Emma Wawrzynek]: You mention briefly in the discussion that you have statistics comparing the accuracy of your model to real data. I think it'd be very important to include those statistics, otherwise it's very hard for readers to evaluate if your model matches real life. You don't really mention otherwise how accurate you perceive the model to be.

[Joshua Hajicek]: The primary role of the model is to remove influences of non-propagating acoustic sources from admittance and impedance, and we are reasonably confident in the model's ability to do that. This model is still early in its development so more work is to validate the individual branches and how well they represent the physiology.

[Emma Wawrzynek]: How did you choose values for the various components in your analogous circuit diagram. I'm specifically interested in how you assigned values to the "TBD" section as we don't know what physically causes it.

[Joshua Hajicek]: The parameters (e.g., K_1 , R_1 , M_1 , and etc.) in the circuit diagram are open parameters. The parameter values are identified by the algorithm described by Lagarias et al. (1998) (see above) which is a multivariable search constrained by minimum and maximum values we set for each parameter. While we are cautious about labeling the 2nd and 4th branches of our model, we know that both are important features for describing the notches in absorbance. The parameter fitting procedure optimizes the parameter values based on the individual data we fit the model.

[Panagiota Kitsopoulos]: Can you talk a more about how you defined the parameters within the middle ear model, did you use the [WAI] data or were the parameters taken from another paper?

[Joshua Hajicek]: The parameters for each ear were individually fit to the data, where the parameter space is constrained by a set of hyperparameters. More physiologically relevant constraints are expected to make the branch outputs more meaningful, but more work is needed to establish them. Each branch of the model has a resonance or anti-resonance associated with it; therefore, the model is essentially decomposing the signal into a set of resonances and anti-resonances hence, the output of the model is a smoothed version of the input.

[Susan Voss]: You highlighted some small differences in middle ear admittance magnitude, around 1-2 kHz, after you applied your model. I am curious, I think those are mean differences from the [28] or so normal ears and the [14] CI implanted ears, is there some sort of confidence interval around those because it did not look like a particularly large difference and I'm just wondering if it was significant?

[Joshua Hajicek]: We addressed this in the manuscript with a Wilcoxon-rank-sum statistic where the differences in admittance showed up either in the magnitude and phase.

[Jont Allen]: There is something called vector fitting and what it does is if you have the input impedance it peels off one element at a time, it is a very tricky method, but extremely well known and documented, works well, free code in MATLAB or Octave, vector fitting, and it will give you, it will fit your data by doing residue expansion and poles, finds the poles and residues, which are equivalent to the zeros, and works fantastically well as long as your data is linear.